

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Aromatic Anil by Pyridinium Chlorochromate

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Manuscript received 24 August 1993, revised 13 December 1993, accepted 31 December 1993

Kinetics of oxidation of aromatic anil by pyridinium chlorochromate (PCC) has been studied at 35° in 70% aqueous acetic acid. Though the versatility of PCC as an oxidant is well known¹, the study on the oxidation of nitrogen containing compounds with PCC is only a few².

Results and Discussion

Kinetics of oxidation of aromatic anil by PCC was investigated at several initial concentrations of the reactants. The oxidation proceeds smoothly at 35° in aqueous acetic acid medium. At low concentrations of PCC and when anil is in large excess, the reaction is found to be first order in PCC. The plots of $\log(a-x)$ against time are found to be linear with a correlation coefficient 0.99, showing a first order dependence in [PCC].

The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_1) calculated at different initial concentrations of the substrate are found to increase linearly with the increase in anil concentration. A plot of $\log k_1$ against $\log [\text{anil}]$ gave a straight line with slope 0.98, the correlation coefficient being 0.98. The rate constants were measured at 30, 35, 40 and 45°. The thermodynamic parameters are as follows: $E_a = 42.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger = -153.1 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta H^\ddagger = 39.9 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta G^\ddagger = 87.1 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. The large negative value of ΔS^\ddagger suggests that the rate-determining transition state is less disorderly than the reactants.

The effect of hydrogen ion concentration on the rate of this oxidation is studied by varying $[\text{H}^+]$ while keeping the concentrations of other reactants constant. A steady increase in the oxida-

tion rate with an increase in the acidity of the medium suggests the formation of protonated PCC in the rate-determining step³. The plot of $\log k_1$ against $\log [\text{H}^+]$ is linear with a slope of nearly two suggesting that two protons may involve in the rate-determining step⁴, one for PCC and the other for anil.

The reaction was carried out at different ionic strengths by altering the concentrations of NaClO_4 and NaCl and keeping the concentrations of other reactants constant. The decrease in the rate with the increase in ionic strength may be due to ion-dipole interaction between protonated anil and protonated PCC which would behave as a dipole. The increase in the percentage of acetic acid in the reaction mixture increased the rate. A straight line is obtained when the percentage of acetic acid is plotted against the rate constant (Table 1). No turbidity was noticed when a clear reaction mixture containing anil and PCC was allowed to stand with a drop of acrylonitrile. It shows that the oxidation process may not involve a free radical mechanism.

Based on the above observations the following mechanism is proposed :

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [SUBSTRATE], [Cl⁻], [ClO₄⁻], [H⁺] AND DIELECTRIC CONSTANT

Temp = 35°, [PCC] = 1 × 10 ⁻³ mol dm ⁻³					
[Anil] × 10 ² mol dm ⁻³	[NaClO ₄] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[NaCl] × 10 ⁴ mol dm ⁻³	[H ⁺] × 10 ² mol dm ⁻³	AcOH-H ₂ O %(v/v)	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹
0.50	—	—	—	70	1.09
0.75	—	—	—	70	1.67
1.00	—	—	—	70	1.83
1.30	—	—	—	70	2.84
1.00	5	—	—	70	1.31
1.00	10	—	—	70	1.12
1.00	20	—	—	70	0.87
1.00	30	—	—	70	0.68
1.00	—	—	12.6	70	2.04
1.00	—	—	14.7	70	2.22
1.00	—	—	20.9	70	3.14
1.00	—	—	25.1	70	3.48
1.00	—	4.95	—	70	1.10
1.00	—	11.90	—	70	0.99
1.00	—	17.90	—	70	0.97
1.00	—	29.80	—	70	0.94
1.00	—	—	—	75	2.37
1.00	—	—	—	80	3.71
1.00	—	—	—	85	5.05

The following rate law can be derived

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[\text{PCC}]}{dt} = K_1 K_2 k_3 [\text{anil}] [\text{PCC}] [\text{H}^+]^2$$

This explains well the observed kinetic results as enumerated earlier.

Experimental

Anil and PCC were prepared by standard procedures⁵. The purity of anil was checked by its m.p while PCC was standardised by iodometric assay. Acetic acid, sulphuric acid, sodium chloride and sodium perchlorate (all AnalaR) were used. All kinetic measurements were made by estimating

iodometrically the oxidant in the aliquot of the reaction mixture. The rate constants were evaluated from the plots of log (a-x) vs time, following the least-squares method and were reproducible within ± 4% error.

The reaction mixtures containing excess of PCC over anil were kept at 35° under kinetic conditions for 24 h. Estimation of the unreacted PCC showed that 1 mole of anil consumed 1 mole of PCC. The reactants in the ratio anil : PCC (1 : 10) in acetic acid-water were kept for 2 days. The acetic acid was neutralised and the reaction mixture was ether-extracted. The dark brown extract, when subjected to tlc gave two distinct spots. On evaporation of ether the products were found to be benzaldehyde which was identified by the isolation of its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative and azobenzene identified by its m.p. (65°) and λ_{max} value (320 nm).

References

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NOTE

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